

Oxidation of some aliphatic aldehydes by tetrakis (pyridine) silver dichromate : A kinetic and mechanistic study[†]

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Manuscript received 28 March 2012, accepted 30 March 2012

Abstract : The oxidation of six aliphatic aldehydes by tetrakis (pyridine) silver dichromate (TPSD) in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) leads to the formation of corresponding carboxylic acids. The reaction is first order each in TPSD. A Michaelis-Menten type of kinetics is observed with respect to the aldehydes. The reaction is catalysed by hydrogen ions, the hydrogen-ion dependence has the form : $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b[\text{H}^+]$. The oxidation of deuteriated acetaldehyde, MeCDO, exhibited a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect ($k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}} = 5.80$ at 298 K). The oxidation of acetaldehyde has been studied in nineteen different organic solvents. The solvent effect has been analysed using Taft's and Swain's multiparametric equations. The rate constants correlate well with Taft's σ^* values; reaction constants being negative. A mechanism involving transfer of hydride ion has been suggested.

Keywords : Aldehydes, correlation analysis, halochromate, kinetics, mechanism, oxidation.

Introduction

Cr^{VI} salts of have long been used as oxidizing reagents in synthetic organic chemistry. However, these salts are drastic and non-selective oxidants. Further, they are insoluble in most of the organic solvents. Thus miscibility is a problem. To overcome these limitations, a large number of organic derivatives of Cr^{VI} have been prepared and used in synthetic organic syntheses as mild and selective oxidants in non-aqueous solvents¹. One such compound is tetrakis (pyridine) silver dichromate (TPSD) reported by Firouzabadi and co-workers². Only a few reports are available in literature regarding the oxidation aspects of TPSD³⁻⁶. It is known that the mode of oxidation depends on the nature of the counter-ion attached to the chromium anion. Therefore, in continuation of our earlier work, we report here the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of six aliphatic aldehydes by TPSD in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) as solvent. The mechanistic aspects are discussed.

The main aims of the present investigation are to (i) determine kinetic parameters and to evaluate the rate laws, (ii) to study the correlation analysis of effect of structure on (iii) and to postulate a suitable mechanism for the oxidation process.

Results and discussion

The rate and other experimental data were obtained for all the aldehydes. Since the results are similar, only representative data are reproduced here.

Stoichiometry : The oxidation of aliphatic aldehydes by TPSD leads to the formation of corresponding carboxylic acids. The stoichiometric determinations indicated the following overall reaction :

Rate laws : The reactions are of first order with respect to TPSD. Further, the pseudo-first order rate constant, k_{obs} is independent of the initial concentration of

[†]In honour of Professor K. B. Pandeya on the occasion of his 70th Birth Anniversary.

TPSD. The reaction rate increases with increase in the concentration of the aldehydes but not linearly (Table 1). The Fig. 1 depicts a typical kinetic run. A plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ against $1/[\text{Aldehyde}]$ is linear ($r > 0.995$) with an intercept on the rate-ordinate. Thus, Michaelis-Menten type

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of acetaldehyde by TPSD at 298 K

10^3 [TPSD] (mol dm ⁻³)	[MeCHO] (mol dm ⁻³)	[TsOH] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)
1.00	0.10	0.00	7.04
1.00	0.20	0.00	10.3
1.00	0.40	0.00	13.3
1.00	0.60	0.00	14.8
1.00	0.80	0.00	15.6
1.00	1.00	0.00	16.2
1.00	1.50	0.00	17.0
1.00	3.00	0.00	18.0
2.00	0.40	0.00	14.4
4.00	0.40	0.00	12.6
6.00	0.40	0.00	14.8
8.00	0.40	0.00	13.0
1.00	0.20	0.00	11.7 ^a

^aContained 0.001 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

Fig. 1. Oxidation of acetaldehyde by TPSD : A typical kinetic run.

kinetics is observed with respect to the aldehydes. This leads to the postulation of following overall mechanism (2) and (3) and rate law (4).

$$\text{Rate} = k_2 K [\text{Aldehyde}] [\text{TPSD}] / (1 + K [\text{Aldehyde}]) \quad (4)$$

The dependence of reaction rate on the reductant concentration was studied at different temperatures and the values of K and k_2 were evaluated from the double reciprocal plots (Fig. 2). The thermodynamic parameters of the complex formation and activation parameters of the decomposition of the complexes were calculated from the values of K and k_2 respectively at different temperatures (Tables 3 and 4).

Fig. 2. Oxidation of aldehyde by TPSD : A double reciprocal plot.

Table 2. Dependence of the reaction rate on hydrogen-ion concentration

[Aldehyde] 0.10 mol dm ⁻³ ; [TPSD] 0.001 mol dm ⁻³ ; Temp. 298 K [TsOH] (mol dm ⁻³)	0.10	0.20	0.40	0.60	0.80	1.00
$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)	8.28	9.81	12.3	15.0	17.1	20.0

Induced polymerization of acrylonitrile/test for free radicals : The oxidation of aldehydes, in an atmosphere of nitrogen, failed to induce polymerisation of acrylonitrile. Further, the addition of acrylonitrile did not affect the rate. This indicates that a one-electron oxidation, giving rise to free radicals, is unlikely in the present reaction (Table 1). To further confirm the absence of free radicals in the reaction pathway, the reaction was carried out in the presence of 0.05 mol dm⁻³ of 2,6-di-*t*-butyl-4-methylphenol (butylated hydroxytoluene or BHT). It was observed that BHT was recovered unchanged, almost quantitatively.

Kinetic isotope effect : To ascertain the importance of the cleavage of the aldehydic-C-H bond in the rate-determining step, the oxidation of deuteriated acetaldehyde

Table 3. Rate constants and activation parameters of the oxidation of aliphatic aldehydes-TPSD complexes

Subst.	$10^4 k_2$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				ΔH^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta S^*$ (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	ΔG^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)
	288 K	298 K	308 K	318 K			
H	1.35	3.33	7.83	17.1	61.9 ± 0.2	104 ± 1	92.9 ± 0.2
Me	18.9	42.3	89.1	180	54.6 ± 0.2	108 ± 1	86.6 ± 0.1
Et	32.4	71.1	144	279	52.1 ± 1.2	112 ± 1	85.3 ± 0.2
Pr	35.1	76.5	158	306	52.4 ± 0.2	110 ± 1	85.1 ± 0.1
Pr ⁱ	52.2	113	229	441	51.6 ± 0.2	110 ± 1	84.1 ± 0.2
ClCH ₂	0.066	0.18	0.48	1.15	70.2 ± 0.4	101 ± 1	99.9 ± 0.3
MeCDO	3.06	7.29	16.2	34.2	58.7 ± 0.2	109 ± 1	90.9 ± 0.2
k_H/k_D	6.12	5.80	5.50	5.26			

Table 4. Formation constants and thermodynamic parameters of the oxidation of aliphatic aldehydes-TPSD complexes

Subst.	K /(dm ³ mol ⁻¹)				$-\Delta H^*$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta S^*$ (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	$-\Delta G^*$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)
	288 K	298 K	308 K	318 K			
H	6.53	5.80	5.04	4.32	12.9 ± 0.4	21 ± 1	6.82 ± 0.3
Me	5.94	5.25	4.51	3.80	13.8 ± 0.5	25 ± 2	6.56 ± 0.4
Et	6.12	5.38	4.70	3.95	13.5 ± 0.5	24 ± 2	6.64 ± 0.4
Pr	5.66	4.95	4.23	3.50	14.6 ± 0.6	28 ± 2	6.42 ± 0.5
Pr ⁱ	5.85	5.15	4.45	3.72	13.9 ± 0.6	25 ± 2	6.52 ± 0.4
ClCH ₂	6.03	5.35	4.62	3.87	13.7 ± 0.6	24 ± 2	6.61 ± 0.5
MeCDO	5.61	4.85	4.15	3.46	14.7 ± 0.5	28 ± 1	6.38 ± 0.4

(MeCDO) was studied. The oxidation of deuteriated acetaldehyde exhibited a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect (Table 3).

Effect of acidity : The reaction is catalysed by hydrogen ions (Table 2). The hydrogen-ion dependence has the following form $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b[\text{H}^+]$. The values of a and b , for acetaldehyde, are $7.15 \pm 0.15 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $12.8 \pm 0.25 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively ($r^2 = 0.9985$).

$$\text{Rate} = k_2 [\text{TPSD}] [\text{Aldehyde}] + k_3 [\text{TPSD}] [\text{Aldehyde}] [\text{TsOH}] \quad (5)$$

Effect of solvents : The oxidation of acetaldehyde was studied in 19 different organic solvents. The choice of solvents was limited due to the solubility of TPSD and its reaction with primary and secondary alcohols. There was no reaction with the solvents chosen. The values of formation constants K and decomposition constants of complex, k_2 are recorded in Table 5.

Table 5. Effect of solvents on the oxidation of acetaldehyde-TPSD complex at 298 K

Solvents	K_* (dm ⁻³ mol ⁻¹)	$10^4 k_2$ (s ⁻¹)	Solvents	K (dm ⁻³ mol ⁻¹)	$10^4 k_2$ (s ⁻¹)
1,2-Dichloroethane	5.45	14.8	Acetophenone	5.55	20.4
Dichloromethane	5.49	12.9	THF	4.77	6.46
DMSO	5.25	42.3	<i>t</i> -Butyl alcohol	5.04	4.57
Acetone	6.03	14.1	1,4-Dioxane	4.59	7.41
DMF	6.45	22.9	1,2-Dimethoxyethane	6.21	3.47
Butanone	6.12	9.77	CS ₂	4.95	1.86
Nitrobenzene	5.94	18.2	Acetic acid	5.86	2.29
Benzene	5.85	5.13	Ethyl acetate	5.66	5.62
Cyclohexane	5.33	0.51			

The entropy and enthalpy of activation of the oxidation of six aldehydes are linearly related ($r = 0.9422$), indicating the operation of compensation effect in this reaction⁷. The value of isokinetic temperature evaluated^{8,9} from this plot is 1668 ± 265 K. The correlation was tested and found genuine by Exners' criterion¹⁰. The isokinetic temperature, calculated from Exner's plot of $\log k_2$ at two extreme temperatures ($r = 0.9999$) is 2053 ± 351 K (Fig. 3). The linear isokinetic correlation suggests that all the aldehydes are oxidized by the same mechanism.

Fig. 3. Exner's isokinetic relationship in the oxidation of aldehydes by TPSD.

Solvent effect : A perusal of the data shows that the formation constants do not vary much with the nature of the solvents. However, the rate constants, k_2 varied considerably with the solvents. The rate constants for oxidation, k_2 , in eighteen solvents (CS_2 was not considered, as the complete range of the solvent parameters was not available) were correlated in terms of the linear solvation energy relationship eq. (6) of Kamlet *et al.*¹¹.

$$\log k_2 = A_0 + p\pi^* + b\beta + \alpha \quad (6)$$

In this equation, π^* represents the solvent polarity, β the hydrogen bond acceptor basicities and α is the hydrogen bond donor acidity. A_0 is the intercept term. It may be mentioned here that out of the 18 solvents, 12 have a value of zero for α . The results of correlation analyses in terms of (6), a biparametric equation involving π^* and β , and separately with π^* and β are given below as eqs. (7)–(10).

$$\log k_2 = -4.10 + 1.56 (\pm 0.23) \pi^* + 0.08 (\pm 0.19) \beta + 0.21 (\pm 0.18) \alpha \quad (7)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8166; sd = 0.21; n = 18; \psi = 0.47$$

$$\log k_2 = -4.15 + 1.64 (\pm 0.22) \pi^* + 0.01 (\pm 0.18) \beta \quad (8)$$

$$R^2 = 0.7989; sd = 0.21; n = 18; \psi = 0.48$$

$$\log k_2 = -4.15 + 1.64 (\pm 0.21) \pi^* \quad (9)$$

$$r^2 = 0.7988; sd = 0.20; n = 18; \psi = 0.46$$

$$\log k_2 = -3.19 + 0.31 (\pm 0.37) \beta \quad (10)$$

$$r^2 = 0.0416; sd = 0.44; n = 18; \psi = 1.01$$

Here n is the number of data points and ψ is the Exner's statistical parameter¹².

Kamlet's¹¹ triparametric equation explains *ca.* 81% of the effect of solvent on the oxidation. However, by Exner's criterion¹² the correlation is not even satisfactory [*cf.* (7)]. The major contribution is of solvent polarity. It alone accounted for *ca.* 80% of the data. Both β and α play relatively minor roles.

The data on the solvent effect were analysed in terms of Swain's equation¹³ of cation- and anion-solvating concept of the solvents also as eq. (11).

$$\log k_2 = aA + bB + C \quad (11)$$

Here A represents the anion-solvating power of the solvent and B the cation-solvating power. C is the intercept term. $(A + B)$ is postulated to represent the solvent polarity. The rates in different solvents were analysed in terms of eq. (8), separately with A and B and with $(A + B)$.

$$\log k_2 = 0.57 (\pm 0.04) A + 1.73 (\pm 0.03) B - 4.41 \quad (12)$$

$$R^2 = 0.9965; sd = 0.03; n = 19; \psi = 0.06$$

$$\log k_2 = 0.32 (\pm 0.57) A - 3.23 \quad (13)$$

$$r^2 = 0.0182; sd = 0.46; n = 19; \psi = 1.02$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.68 (\pm 0.10) B - 4.23 \quad (14)$$

$$r^2 = 0.9403; sd = 0.11; n = 19; \psi = 0.25$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.34 \pm 0.15 (A + B) - 4.38 \quad (15)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8250; sd = 0.19; n = 19; \psi = 0.43$$

The rates of oxidation of acetaldehyde in different solvents showed an excellent correlation in Swain's equation [*cf.* (12)] with the cation-solvating power playing the major role. In fact, the cation-solvation alone accounts for *ca.* 94% of the data. The correlation with the anion-solvating power was very poor. The solvent pola-

rity, represented by $(A + B)$, also accounted for *ca.* 83% of the data. In view of the fact that solvent polarity is able to account for *ca.* 83% of the data, an attempt was made to correlate the rate with the relative permittivity of the solvent. However, a plot of $\log k_2$ against the inverse of the relative permittivity is not linear ($r^2 = 0.5214$; $sd = 0.54$; $\psi = 0.71$).

Correlation analysis of reactivity : The rates of the oxidation of six aldehydes show an excellent correlation with Taft's σ^* substituent constants¹⁴, the reaction constant being negative (Table 6). The negative polar reaction constant indicates an electron-deficient carbon centre in the transition state of the rate-determining step.

Temp. (K)	ρ^*	r^2	sd	ψ
288	-2.34 ± 0.01	0.9998	0.001	0.02
298	-2.26 ± 0.02	0.9989	0.002	0.04
308	-2.15 ± 0.01	0.9999	0.004	0.01
318	-2.08 ± 0.02	0.9998	0.007	0.02

Mechanism :

In aqueous solutions most aliphatic aldehydes exist predominantly in the hydrate form¹⁵ and in many oxidations, in aqueous solutions, it has been postulated that the hydrate is the reactive species. However, owing to the non-aqueous nature of the solvent in the present reaction, only the free carbonyl form can be the reactive species.

There is no kinetic evidence for the formation of an intermediate in the present reaction, however, its formation in small amounts can not be ruled out. The presence of a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect ($k_H/k_D = 5.80$ at 298 K), confirms that the aldehydic C-H bond is cleaved in the rate-determining step. The large negative value of the polar reaction constant together with the substantial deuterium isotope effect indicates that the transition state approaches a carbocation in character. Hence, transfer of a hydride ion from the aldehyde to the oxidant is suggested. The hydride ion transfer mechanism is also supported by major role of cation-solvating power of the solvents.

It is of interest to compare here the mode of oxidation of aliphatic aldehydes by PFC¹⁶, PBC¹⁷, QFC¹⁸ and TPSD. The oxidation by QFC, PFC and TPSD presented a similar kinetic picture, i.e. Michaelis-Menten type ki-

netics, with respect to the reductants, while, by the PBC¹⁷ reactions are of first order with respect to the reductants. It seems that the values of the formation constants for the intermediates are very small in case of PBC. This resulted in the favour of second-order kinetics. Kinetic isotope effects, solvent effects and the dependence of the hydrogen ions are of similar nature in all these reactions, for which essentially similar mechanisms have been proposed.

Scheme 1. Acid-independent path.

Scheme 2. Acid-dependent path.

Experimental

Materials : TPSD was prepared by the reported method² and its purity checked by an iodometric determinations. Solutions of formaldehyde were prepared by heating *para*-formaldehyde and passing its vapours in DMSO. The amount of HCHO in DMSO was determined by chromotropic acid method¹⁹. Other aldehydes were

commercial products and were used as such. *p*-Toluenesulphonic acid (TsOH) was used as a source of hydrogen ions. Deuteriated acetaldehyde (MeCDO) was obtained from Sigma Chemicals. Solvents were purified by their usual methods²⁰.

Product analysis : The product analysis was carried out under kinetic conditions. In a typical experiment, acetaldehyde (4.4 g, 0.1 mol) and TPSD (7.48 g, 0.01 mol) were dissolved in DMSO (100 ml) and the reaction mixture was allowed to stand for *ca.* \approx 24 to ensure completion of the reaction. It was then rendered alkaline with NaOH, filtered and the filtrate was reduced to dryness under pressure. The residue was acidified with perchloric acid and extracted with diethyl ether (5%, 50 ml). The ether extract was dried (MgSO₄) and treated with 10 ml of thionyl chloride. The solvent was allowed to evaporate. Dry methanol (7 ml) was added and the HCl formed was removed in a current of dry air. The residue was dissolved in diethyl ether (200 ml) and the ester content was determined colorimetrically as Fe^{III} hydroxymate by the procedure of Hall and Schaefer²¹. Several determinations indicated a 1 : 1 stoichiometry. The oxidation state of chromium in a completely reduced reaction mixture, determined by iodometric titrations was 3.95 ± 0.15 .

Kinetic measurements : Pseudo-first order conditions were attained by keeping an excess ($\times 15$ or greater) of the [Aldehyde] over [TPSD]. The solvent was DMSO, unless mentioned otherwise. All reactions were carried out in flasks blackened from the outside to prevent any photochemical reactions. The reactions were carried out at constant temperature (± 0.1 K) and were followed up to 80% of the extent of reaction, by monitoring the decrease in [TPSD] at 352 nm. The pseudo-first order rate constant, k_{obs} , was computed from the linear least-squares plot of log [TPSD] versus time. Duplicate runs showed that the rate constants were reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$. The second order rate constant, k_2 , was calculated from the relation : $k_2 = k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{Aldehyde}]$.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to the UGC, New Delhi for financial support as BSR, One Time Grant No. F. 4-10/2010(BSR)

dated 07.03.2012 and to Professor K. K. Banerji, Dean Sciences, NLU, Mandore, Jodhpur, for critical and valuable suggestions.

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